

Speculation on Quantum Mechanics and Special Relativity

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In this note, we consider the classical Action = $\int L dt$ which is equal to $Et - px$ with $E = \frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ and $p = m_0 v$. We also consider the factor $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ for a photon which follows from Maxwell's equations. We argue that a probabilistic view of a free quantum particle could lead to the idea of $\exp(iEt - px)$ (nonrelativistic). This expression already links $p = m_0 v$ with x i.e. p is a wavelength. Given that $p = m_0 v$ i.e. rest mass flux, we argue that $E = \frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ might actually be $E = b_1 m_0 + b_2 \frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ with b_2 rendering the second term small. (This places a limit then on the maximum v .) Next, we argue that $Et - px$ should be invariant when viewed from different frames on the basis of probability. Finally, we note that $Et - px$ is related to $Et(1 - v^2/c^2)$. For a particle at rest, $E = m_0 c^2$, but if E and t are on the same footing from quantum probabilistic ideas, then $m_0 c^2$ and t are energy and time in the rest frame and $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $t / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ are energy and time seen from the lab frame for invariance to hold. Such a picture yields the nonrelativistic kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ upon expanding E for small v . Thus, we speculate that one may obtain special relativistic results from quantum probabilistic arguments. [As a note, in (1) Lorentz boosts are obtained by analyzing transformations of quarks together with the Pauli principle, but the idea is to also argue that special relativity follows from quantum mechanics.]

Photon and $Et - px$

It was already known by Maxwell in the 1800s that $\cos(Et - px)$ was part of a solution of the Electric and B (magnetic) fields of a photon which followed from Maxwell's equations without source terms. $\cos(Et - px)$ mimicked a wave form $\cos(\omega t - kx)$ where ω is $2\pi \times \text{frequency}$ and $k = 2\pi / \text{wavelength}$ which existed for physical waves on a string. In the case of a photon, which was known to exhibit wave properties, E (energy) becomes associated with ω and p with k . Thus, there is a link between p and x and E and t . Momentum, however, is also related to force in the Newtonian sense as can be seen from experiments. Furthermore, momentum is not simply related to velocity as photons all move at a speed of c , but may have different wavelengths and so momenta.

It was also known before 1905 by Lorentz and Einstein that Maxwell's equations are consistent with special relativity. Today, there are papers (1) which argue that Maxwell's equations are actually quantum equations with the wavefunction for the photon being $EI + iB$ where EI is the electric field and B the magnetic. In that case, the requirements of special relativity and "quantum mechanics" go hand in hand for the electromagnetic case. Lastly, Einstein postulated in 1905 that the speed of light in vacuum c was the maximum speed at which energy could travel i.e. an upper bound exists on the speed of a particle with mass.

Classical Et-px

The form $Et - px$ is present in classical mechanics as it is equivalent to the classical action for a particle moving at a constant velocity v :

$$\text{Action} = \int dt L \quad \text{where } H=E= pv - L \quad \text{so } \text{Action} = -Et + \int p dx/dt dt = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

Here $p=mv$ and $E = .5mv^2$ ((2)). The expressions in ((2)) are not symmetrical. If one considers p as an energy flux, then one might argue that energy should be related to mv . In such a case, $.5mv^2$ might be a correction term, but it should be small.

From the photon, one knows that: $E=pc$, so one may postulate that:

$E_{\text{particle}} = pc = mv/c$. In such a case mv/c has dimensions of energy, but is not the full energy of a moving particle because a $.5mv^2$ correction term must arise.

Thus, one might think of E and $E/c = mv$.

Probabilistic Arguments and Et - px

As noted above, the classical action = $-Et + px$. Then, $d/dt \text{ Action} = -E$ and $d/dx \text{ Action} = p$ for a particle moving at constant v . In general $v=x/t$ so one should not vary x and t independently. This seems to suggest a kind of error or fluctuation in the classical action. For example, $d/dx \text{ Action} = p$ so an error in x of dX leads to an error in the action of $p dX$. Already the idea of a p dependent error arises. If one considers a statistical situation, one may argue that a constant particle density $P(x)$ should be considered. How may this be linked to $Et-px$? A solution is through:

$$\text{Conditional probability} = \exp(ipx - iEt) \quad ((2))$$

The modulus is 1, yet there is energy flow through space. Furthermore, p and x are on the same footing as are Et .

One may ask how the phase should change if viewed from a different frame moving at a constant velocity v_1 ? $px-Et$ is the phase of the probability and if one argues that this is frame independent, then $px-Et$ should be a constant.

$$\text{Next, one may write, using } v=x/t, : \quad -px + Et = Et(1 - vv/c^2) .$$

This yields a kind of symmetry for E, p i.e. mv/c and $mv=p$, i.e. energy and energy flux.

Alternatively, one may set $E= mv/c + B(v)$ where $B(v)$ is a correction term. Then, p is defined as:

$p = (m_0 c^2 + B(v)) / c v$ $v = E / c v$ i.e. one wishes p to be energy flux ((2b))
 The result is: $E t - p x = E t (1 - v^2/c^2)$

For $v=0$, one has $m_0 c t$. If the particle is moving at speed v , then by invariance:

$$m_0 c t (1 - v^2/c^2) = m_0 c t \quad ((3))$$

Thus, m_0 and t_0 in the rest frame should be viewed from the lab frame as having new values. If E and t are treated as being on the same footing, then:

$$\text{Energy in the lab} = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad t_{\text{lab}} = t_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((4))$$

This yields special relativity results. [One might argue that E is like $1/t$ and p like $1/x$ so $E t$, but that is only related to units, not the essence of E and p under transformation.) ((4)) holds for $x=0$ in both the rest and lab frame.

Thus, a person in the lab sees a different energy, but the overall phase $p x - E t$ is the same whether evaluated in the lab or rest frame. This phase is related to the conditional probability $\exp(i p x - i E t)$ of the particle.

Finally, it may be seen that $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ leads to a correction term after $m_0 c^2$ of $.5 m_0 v^2$ which is the usual kinetic energy in nonrelativistic theory.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the form $E t - p x$ is present in classical theory i.e. is equivalent to classical Action for a particle moving at constant speed v . E , however, is $.5 m_0 v^2$ in such a case. If one wishes to have symmetry i.e. E and $E/c v = p$ then:

$$E t - p x = E t (1 - v^2/c^2)$$

Arguing that in a probabilistic theory i.e. quantum mechanics, $\exp(i p x - i E t)$ represents a conditional probability which describes dynamics, but has a modulus 1 which indicates a particle has $P(x) = \text{constant}$, $E t - p x$ may be invariant with respect to boosts. In such a case, treating E and t as variables on the same footing:

$$E_{\text{lab}} = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad t_{\text{lab}} = t_{\text{rest}} / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

p and x should also be treated on equal footing because they appear as $p x$ in $-E t + p x$:

$p = E/c v$ E and t transform in the same manner so p transforms as x in a hand-wavy sense.

It may be noted that $E_t - p_x$ looks very much like a dot product of -1 (iE , p vector) and $(it, x$ vector). Thus, one may have a kind of constant length squared as different Lorentz boosts behave as a generalized kind of "rotation".

Ultimately, we argue that one may obtain relativistic results from a probabilistic model created from $E_t - p_x$ converted into $\exp(ipx - iEt)$. This probabilistic picture already holds in nonrelativistic cases, but in order to have symmetry one suggests that $p = E/cv$ i.e. there is energy and energy flow. Using this assumption, one obtains a result which yields an energy correction to $m_0 c^2$ of $.5mv^2$ i.e. the nonrelativistic dynamical energy.

We point out that in (1), the authors derive Lorentz transformations by considering the two quarks which make up a fermion (e.g. nucleon) together with the Pauli principle. They argue that special relativity arises from quantum mechanics at this level.

References

1. Kerner, R. Quantum Physical Origins of Lorentz Transformations
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